

THEORETICAL AND LEGAL BASIS OF PATRIOTIC EDUCATION OF YOUTH IN THE EDUCATION SYSTEM

Kuchmuradova Zulfiya Urinboevna
TASHKENT CITY OLMAZOR DISTRICT
SCHOOL 249, TEACHER OF
HISTORY OF AND TEACHER
OF EDUCATION

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6942231>

In today's era of globalization, formation of a sense of patriotism in young people, and determination of a high and stable position in life is becoming more important. Increasing the activity of young people, raising a generation with a strong moral and socio-political outlook, and achieving the stability of society by forming patriotic skills in them is becoming more important than ever. Today, in the ideological landscape of the world, the trend of ideological conflict, which manifests the goals and aspirations of competing political forces, is intensifying.

Therefore, in order to create a unique ideological immunity by acquiring patriotic skills in young people, it is important to evaluate the ideologies that reflect the values of the modern world and their place in socio-political and cultural-ideological processes, to deeply understand their content, to give up the homeland in young people, to preserve the traditions of our nation for centuries. One of the urgent issues is to pay attention to the formation of the skills to see new ideological threats that lead to the occurrence of cases of disrespect for their customs.

Therefore, it is of urgent importance to develop modern directions of formation of patriotic skills in young people, to educate young people who can resist modern ideological threats.

"Strategy of actions for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021", adopted by the President of our country Shavkat Mirziyoyev in February 2017, as a new stage of the social and legal relations of the state and society, management and all spheres of the economy, including the spiritual, educational and social sphere is being considered.

Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On State Policy Regarding Youth" adopted on September 15, 2016, Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 28, 2017 "On increasing the effectiveness of spiritual and educational work and raising the development of the field to a new level" PQ-3160, Republic of Uzbekistan Decree of the President of February 2, 2018 "On measures to radically improve activities in the field of supporting women and strengthening the family institution", Decree No. PF-5416 of the President of the

Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 16, 2018 "On measures to fundamentally improve the activity of the religious and educational sphere", Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 12, 2018 "In order to widely study and promote the creative heritage of our great scholars, writers and thinkers" Decision No. PQ-3721 "On organizing reading contests among young people", the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated August 4, 2018 "System of raising the moral and educational level of military personnel of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan" on radical improvement" Decision No. PQ-3898, Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated August 14, 2018 "On measures to bring up young people spiritually, morally and physically, and raise the quality of their education system to a new level" PQ-3907- Decision No. PQ-4038 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan of November 28, 2018 "On approval of the concept of further development of national culture in the Republic of Uzbekistan", This dissertation serves to a certain extent in the fulfillment of the tasks specified in the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 3, 2019 "On additional measures to increase the effectiveness of spiritual and educational work" No. PQ-4307.

There are several tasks in the analysis of innovative methods of improving patriotic skills in young people.

- Explain the essence of the concepts of patriotism and nationalism and their ideological and legal basis;
- To show the theoretical and historical roots of the ideas of patriotism and nationalism;
- To shed light on the specific features of the experiences of developed countries in the formation of patriotic skills;
- To demonstrate innovative approaches in the Central Asian countries in the formation of patriotic skills in young people;
- Formation of patriotism skills in young people by creating the image of a "national hero", development of practical suggestions on existing problems;
- It consists in solving the tasks of developing a scientific conclusion and specific practical proposals regarding the prospects of national brands in the field of ICT and electronic commerce in the formation of patriotic skills in young people. In general, it is necessary to implement technologies of formation of patriotism and nationalism skills in young people by means of telecommunication achievements. In this, the role of television, Internet, and especially social networks is incomparable. In particular, the need to create the image of a

national hero is one of the widely tested methods not only in our republic, but also on a global scale.

In the 20th century, the heroes created by the Hollywood and Bollywood film industries fundamentally changed the thinking of not only the nations, but also the youth of the whole world. One of the new approaches in this regard is to show our compatriots who have made certain achievements while working abroad as an example of the heroes of the country who raised the Uzbek name to the blue, without criticizing the conditions of the new Uzbekistan.

List of references used:

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the strategy of actions for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan" // Collection of legal documents of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2017, No. 6, Article 70.
2. Decree No. PF-5416 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 16, 2018 "On measures to fundamentally improve the activities of the religious and educational sphere".
3. Decision No. PQ-4038 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 28, 2018 "On approval of the concept of further development of national culture in the Republic of Uzbekistan",
4. Decision PQ-4307 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan of May 3, 2019 "On additional measures to increase the effectiveness of spiritual and educational work"
5. Abu Nasr Farabi. City of virtuous people. - Tashkent: "People's heritage named after Abdullah Kadiri" publishing house, 1993.
6. Bekmurodov M. Uzbek mentality. - Tashkent: Info capital Group, 2011.
7. Brzezinski 3.B. Vybor. Global domination or global leadership? - M.: International Relations, 2004.
8. Boboev H., Khasanov S. "Avesta" is our spirituality". - Tashkent: Adolat, 2001.

